

Modeling the behavior of farmers in rural areas towards the change of agricultural land use (Case of study: West Azarbaijan Province)

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ABSTRACT: West azerbaijan province is one of the strategic agricultural and horticultural areas in iran. That during recent decades, part of its most fertile agricultural land has been removed from the production cycle and has been changed to multiple uses. This trend is expected to continue or accelerate in the future. In the not-so distant years, we should expect various social economic and environmental effects from this process. Therefore, the present research has analyzed the behavior of agricultural land use change in rural areas of west azarbaijan province. The statistical population of the research was all farmers in rural areas, 749 people were selected as a sample. The instrument of data collection was a questionnaire, which showed the validity and reliability of the questionnaire by cronbakh alpha , AVE and CR.

In Order to set the theoretical framework of the research, the combination of the (TPB), theory of planned behavior, the integrated theory of acceptance and use of (UTAUT), technology, the (IBM) comprehensive behavioral theory and the (NAM) norm activation theory were used. data processing was done using (AMOS) software. The results of the research show that the behavior of agricultural land use change under study is at on average level. Also, the results of the structural equations showed that the variables of behavioral intention to change the use of agricultural land environmental conditions, facility conditions, perceived behavior control, attitude towards the behavior, moral norm, and mental norm have an effect on the behavior of changing the use of agricultural land in the rural areas of province. Also 79% of the above-mention agricultural land use change behavior variable is explained. The research results confirm the theories of TPB, IBM, NAM and UTAUT.

Keywords: Agricultural Land Use Change, Agriculture, Behavior, Geographic Information System,

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1. Introduction

In agriculture, sustainable development is a system comprised of the interactions among various and numerous factors. The aim of these interactions is to improve the living standards of the present generation and those to come. (Tilman et al, 2018). Therefore,

sustainable and consistent development as a building block in planning systems has been embraced by all the dimensions of human life. (Yin et al, 2014). Among these, the agricultural dimension is one of the most sensitive ones, where suitable and sustainable efficiency is pivotal (Liu et al, 2016). Further, it could be stated that water and soil are considered as the most significant production factors in the agricultural sector (FAOSTAT, 2016), on which the survival of human communities depends, in such a way that over 97% of the world's food is gained from this input (soil) (Gerrard, 2014). Therefore, preservation of soil resources and agricultural lands are of utmost importance in sustainable agriculture and production of food, and, finally, in achieving food security (Savari et al, 2020; Engler et al, 2016). Today, changes in land use are one of the most severe challenges of the 21st century (FAO, 2012). In fact, it could be stated that changes in the use type of agricultural lands are the second fundamental issue Iranian farmers are struggling with after climate change (such as droughts and water scarcity) (Mousavi and Yazdanpanah, 2021). These changes are examples of unsuccessful market mechanisms which have failed to help preserve the environment (Doroudian and Doroudian, 2017). Thus, proper application of agricultural lands is stated to be the main root of planning for sustainable development in agriculture because practical planning in agriculture plays a major role in spatial- positional organization of villages, agricultural economy and preservation of the environment (Mehri et al, 2013).

In this regard, the issue of use change in developing countries is even more important due to weak management systems and disorganized economic and political structures (Long et al, 2017). In fact, concerns and discussions on land use and environmental changes are gaining momentum ever more seriously. In such a condition, sustainable land use has turned into a significant analytical-political issue (Longley and Mesev, 2000). As a result, lands and their manner of usage are major issues for all human communities- especially for rural communities where the subsistence of many is directly dependant on such sources (Schirmer et al, 2009). Land use is extremely interrelated with many economic, social, political and environmental processes (Qarani Arani, et al, 2019). These processes changed in various times and spaces and encompass a complex range of interactions among environmental and human factors (Ustaoglu et al, 2016). Having changed land usage, man has exacerbated severe threats in biodiversity, carbon dispense and reduction of non-specific services of the ecosystem. Therefore, it is necessary to understand the vast range of the fundamental reasons for changes in land use on various scales of decision making and find the factors determining the spatial models of these changes (Piquer- Rodriguez et al, 2018).

The progression of change and transformation of land use and their distribution worldwide demonstrates that until 2050, the area of settlements will be increased from 1 to 3 percent of the total earth lands to about 4 to 5 percent, if no preservation policy is taken. (UNEP, 2014). In Iran, about 11 percent of the total land area can be used for agriculture and the annual area under cultivation of crops for the years between 2003 and 2021 demonstrates a descending trend (Ministry of Agricultural Jihad, 2021). During the recent decades, the usage type of over one million acres of agricultural lands has been changed (Qarani Arani, et al, 2019). Unofficial statistics show that every year the average area of the national lands which fall victims to change of use is about 8000 acres; if this number is added to the area of agricultural lands with legal usage, it will hit over 10,000 acres a year (Mohammad Sharifi, et al 2020). Therefore, the uncontrolled change of usage in rural and agricultural lands is a key challenge in Iran (Salimi Matin & Riahi, 2020). As reported by the

Iranian Parliament, for the years, 1980, 1982, 1990, 2002, 2005, and 2021, the areas of lands cultivated have been 13.7, 13.9, 18.2, 18.1, and 15.6 respectively. In other words, after the initial ascending trend, we can witness the start of the descending trend in the area of agricultural lands accompanied by the increase in the pace of change of the land use into non-agricultural usage. In the year 2009, National agricultural lands per capita were 0.235 acres, while this number fell to around 0.176 acres in 2021. Also, studies show that West Azerbaijan, as one of Iran's strategic regions in agriculture and gardening, has not been an exception to this rule and over the recent decades, a section of the most productive agricultural lands of this province has been removed from production cycle and changed into other various usages. Based on the data published by the Ministry of Agricultural Jihad of West Azerbaijan province, for the years between 2001 and 2021, 1353 acres of lands with the potential for cultivation have been changed into industrial, residential, villa and other usages (Agricultural Jihad Organization of West Azerbaijan, 2021). Studies also show that over 600 cases of illegal change of land use for the agricultural lands of West Azerbaijan have been registered in 2021 (Agricultural Jihad Organization of West Azerbaijan, 2021). Further, the agricultural lands per capita of the year 2011 in the western Azerbaijan province were about 0.333 acres, while this number has plummeted to 0.286 acres for the year 2021 (Agricultural Jihad Organization of West Azerbaijan, 2021). Based on what was stated and the fact that changes in land use over the last 50 years have occurred faster than any other period in the Iranian history, it should be said that West Azerbaijan province has had the highest number of changes in land use between 2016 to 2021 (Agricultural Jihad Organization of Western Azerbaijan, 2021).

Exclusion of productive agricultural lands from the production cycle is not remediable easily and within a short period. Soil production is not controlled by man powers, but it can be preserved by modern man (Kalali Moghadam, 2015). Hence, since rural economy is interrelated with agricultural economy and lands are one of the main resources for production in the rural and agricultural sectors (Sadeghloo et al, 2019), uncontrolled changes in the usage of agricultural and rural lands have been turned into one of the major challenges of this region. Due to the consequences land use change brings to the ecosystem and man's life (Fox et al, 2017), it could be said that studying these changes is a key factor in understanding the interactions between the natural environment and the human factors (Cegielska et al., 2018). Therefore, since human behavior is the main root of environmental issues (Zandalinas et al., 2021; Davis et al., 2011), the behavior of exploiters has played a key role in the improvement of management of natural resources and environmental sustenance. Therefore, in order to curb the change in agricultural land use and, as a result, to reduce food insecurity, study of farmers' behavior as the largest group of land users and food producers seems to be necessary. The first step in this path is to understand the present behavior of farmers in changing the land usages. Various researches have been conducted on the factors contributing to changes in the usages of agricultural lands, each of them studying different variables. But in these researches, human behavior toward such changes has been ignored or received little attention. Therefore, the main problems being addressed by this research are: "how frequent are land Use Change Behaviors And Activities Among The Farmers Of Rural Areas Of West Azerbaijan Province? What factors contribute to land use change behavior by the farmers of rural areas of West Azerbaijan Province? To find the answers to these questions, the present research both analyses the various behaviors of the said farmers toward land use change and identifies the factors and conditions contributing to such behaviors, so that we

may predict the behaviors of rural farmers during crises and, finally, achieve scientific and more suitable solutions to address the phenomenon of land use change

2. Review of studies

Definitions of Concepts

Land use has been defined as exploiting lands to meet human needs, which is a formal economic concept and enjoys a vast application covering human interrelations and relations between human and the environment (Reetz and Brummer, 2011). It should also be noted that land use is not a one-dimensional concept; rather, it is a complex combination of various features including ownership, body, structure, and space (Nordborg et al, 2017). Land use is one of the key issues in agricultural economy and sustainable development of agriculture. It brings about considerable social and economic advantages; yet, its drastic costs to the environment come first (Wu, 2008). Thus, suitable use of agricultural lands has been identified as the hard core of planning for sustainable development in agriculture; the reason is that applied agricultural planning plays a major role in Spatial-positional organization of villages, agricultural economy and preservation of the environment (Mehri et al., 2013). Change of land use means change in the type of use and changes in the manner of dispersion and the spatial models of a landscape (Dempsey et al, 2017) which also results in the changes in the ratio of the area of that use type, that is, the structure of land use (Salimi Matin and Riahi, 2020). In fact, changes in land use are defined by the positional and chronological interactions of biophysical and human factors at different scales (Lou et al., 2010). Land use change has resulted in the destruction of a significant section of agricultural lands. The social, cultural and economic consequences of these changes are considerable from the perspective of food security and sustainable employment of rural communities (Bahremand Paskeh & Kavosi Kalashemi, 2020). Land use is closely related to many economic, social, political and environmental processes (Qarani Arani et al, 2019). These processes change over time and space and encompass a complex range of interactions among the environment and human factors. (Ustaoglu et al, 2016). Analysis of land use change is, basically, an analysis between the relationship between human and lands (Ahmadpoor & Alavi, 2014). In fact, changes in land use in rural areas are the result of direct and indirect influence man has made on the environment. (Faal Jalali et al., 2021). Also, the role of human factors in land use change has been mentioned in many researches (Mohammadzadeh, et al., 2020; Amirnezhad, 2013; Karali et al., 2011).

In general, it was stated that the source of the crises and issues related to agriculture such as changes in land use is both the inappropriate human behavior and environmental factors such as climate change, droughts and governance-related and political factors. Various researches have been made regarding factors contributing to use change in agricultural lands, each having studied different variables; but these studies have failed to consider man's behavior towards land use change or have made little consideration of such a factor. In this regard, as put by Jaccard and Blanton (Jaccard & Blanton, 2005), behavior is defined as any open and denotable action conducted by an individual, a group of people, or a living system (such as a business, a city or a nation). On this basis, considering the theoretical foundations and the researches conducted, it could be concluded that change of land use should be approached as a behavior. Different theories

explain behavior through various perceptual and socio-cognitive processes (Mitter et al., 2019).

Theoretical Framework

The most popular theories in behavioral psychology commonly used in the study of the factors affecting farmers' behavior are Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), Self-efficacy theory, IBM model, Triandis's Interpersonal behavior, and UTAUT. Therefore, in order to set the main theoretical framework of the research, the theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) was referenced. This theory (Ajzen, 1991) is a frequent and familiar framework to explain and predict human behavior; further, it has been used vastly to model and explain farmers' behavior (Sok et al., 2020). In fact, this model has often been applied as an appropriate conceptual framework in review articles to study farmers' behavior in different aspects of decision-making (Keykhosravi et al., 2023; Dessart et al., 2019; Gilbert & Rushton, 2018; Fielding & Hornsey, 2016). In effect, TBA is derived from the socio-cognitive theory which explains the individuals' conscious behavior (Rahimi Feizabadi et al., 2016). In this theory, behavior is the central actor determined by the individual's intentions (behavioral purpose) in which the behavioral intentions are, in turn, predicted by the perceived behavioral control, attitudes, and subjective norms (Ajzen, 1991). The principal mechanism of TBA, which is founded on TRA, is based on the assumption that an individual's behavior is influenced by his dispositions (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Although the success of TBA in prediction of behavior has been established (asrari et al., 2022; Sok et al., 2020), other researches have demonstrated that adding some variables to this theory can strengthen its power of prediction (Yazanpanah et al., 2014; Whitmarsh and Oneill, 2010; Fielding et al., 2008). Accordingly, in the present research, some other variables were borrowed from other famous theories such as IBM, NAM, and UTAUT and added to TBA. Also, considering other studies conducted in this field, the variable "environmental conditions" which includes proximity to village or city, access to asphalt-paved roads, and being located at a tourist attraction area was also added to this theory.

Four predictors of behavioral dispositions of UTAUT are: performance expectation (perceived usefulness), attempt expectation (perception of easy usage), social impact (subjective norm) and facilitating conditions. In general, all these structures can explain 70% of the changes in behavioral intentions (Lu et al., 2009). Performance expectation represents the extent to which the individual believes that using the system can benefit him in improving his professional performance. By attempt expectation how much the system is easy to work is meant. Social impact or influence refers to a condition in which the individual perceives that authorized people need him to use a technological system. Facilitating conditions denotes the extent to which the individual believes that the necessary organizational and technical infrastructure to support system exploitation is available (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Behavioral intention is defined as the degree of an individual's readiness to demonstrate a certain behavior (Veronikis et al., 2011).

IBM is comprised of the structure of TRA, TBA, Self-efficiency theory and other major theories of the behavior field. In IBM, an individual is not probable to perform a suggested behavior. This model is comprised of four main components which directly affect the behavior:

1. Knowledge and skill to conduct the behavior,
2. Prominence of behavior,

3. Environmental constraints,
4. Habits.

Three factors are significant in determining whether the behavioral intention can lead to the performance of behavior or not: first, even if the individual has a high behavioral intention, does he enjoy the necessary knowledge and skill to conduct it?; second, the environmental constraints which make conducting the behavior extremely difficult or not difficult should not be present; and third, the behavior should be important and prominent for the individual (Glanz et al., 2008).

Norm Activation Model (NAM), focusing on philanthropic behavior, has a rather different perspective; that is, it means a behavior demonstrating loss of personal interests in favor of others. In this regard, the behavior of an environmental advocate may be considered as a type of philanthropic behavior, because it involves losing one's personal interests in favor of the environment. Moral considerations play a vital role here in such a way that it is assumed that obligations to the behavior and intentions of an environmental advocate be determined as much as people feel a moral obligation to perform the action (moral norms) (Abrahamse et al., 2009). These moral norms which reflect the individual's value system in a certain condition should be activated before they are considered as a determining factor of behavior (Klockner, 2013). Accordingly, Showartz (Showartz, 1994) suggested two pre-conditions to activate moral norms: first, the individual should be aware of what consequences his action may have on the well-being of others (awareness of consequences); second, the individual should feel a personal responsibility to conduct that action (responsibility attribution). If the individual is not able to activate moral norms, no action may be acknowledged suitably and, as a result, no environment supporting action will be taken (Turaga et al., 2010). Additionally, as put by Showartz (Showartz, 1994), moral norms are activated by other key variables. Firstly, the problem is awareness of needs which refers to how much the individual is aware of the necessity for assistance (Klockner, 2013). In fact, awareness of the need is dependent on how much the individual is focused on the existence of a person or an abstract entity (for instance, change of land use) (Harland et al, 2007). In other research, the following can be mentioned, including: Rahmani (Rahmani et al, 2021) studied Providing health, safety and environmental management program in metal mining industry (including case study). Ganjali (Ganjali et al, 2023) studied Strategic analysis of household hazardous waste reduction. Ganjali (Ganjali et al, 2023) studied Investigating the relationship between environmental awareness and the level of education and occupation of people. Taghipour. (Taghipour, 2023) studied A review of the sustainability indicators' application in vehicle routing problem. Taghipour (Taghipour et al, 2023) studied Strategic HR Maintenance: Impact of Organizational Support and Culture on Employee Commitment. Hazrati (Hazrati et al, 2023) studied Designing a Model of Waste Management for Sustainable Rural Development (Case Study: Villages of Gilan Province). Alamdar khoolaki. (Alamdar khoolaki et al, 2019) studied Effect of integrated marketing communication on brand value with the role of agencies reputation (including case study). Baghipour sarami. (Baghipour sarami et al, 2016) studied Modeling of nurses' shift work schedules according to ergonomics: A case study in Imam Sajjad (As) Hospital of Ramsar. Ghadamzan Jalali. (Ghadamzan Jalali et al, 2020) studied Explain the relationship between intellectual capital, organizational learning and employee performance of Parsian Bank Branches in Gilan province. Taghipour. (Taghipour et al, 2018) studied The impact of working capital management on the performance of firms listed in Tehran Stock Exchange

(TSE). Taghipour.(Taghipour et al, 2016) studied Assessment of the Relationship Between Knowledge Management Implementation and Managers Skills (Case Study: Reezmoj System Company in Iran) . Taghipour. (Taghipour et al, 2018) studied Study of the Application of Risk Management in the Operation and Maintenance of Power Plant Projects”. Taghipour.(Taghipour et al, 2015) studied Evaluation of the Relationship between Occupational Accidents and Usage of Personal Protective Equipment in an Auto Making Unit” . Secondly, it is the efficacy of result, which means identification of actions to meet other people's needs or of things valuable for the person (Steg & De Groot, 2010). In this regard, Harland et al. (Harland et al., 2007) believe that many social issues, especially environmental ones are related to collective actions and are connected to studies about the efficacy of result. Thirdly, self-efficacy means the perceived ability to perform a behavior. In fact, it involves people's evaluation of the factors facilitating or hindering a behavior and it includes their perception of how much they perform it (Hurlimann et al., 2009). Fourthly, it is denial of responsibility, which is referred to individuals' willingness to deny their responsibilities to avoid the consequences their behaviors bring about for the well-being of others (Harland et al., 2007). In the norm activation model, it is assumed that all these variables affect the feelings predicted from sin or pride through moral norms (Onwezen et al., 2013). Feeling of guilt is a defined painful sense that is created in an individual when they are faced with a bad event. In contrast, pride is a defined positive feeling and is formed in an individual when they encounter a good event (Bamberg & Moser, 2007). The feelings of pride and sin are sourced in an individual's consciousness. Conscious feelings encompass a wide range of feelings such as the feelings of shame, pride and regret (Onwezen et al., 2013). These conscious feelings, formed by the individual's self-evaluation of standards and moral norms, in turn, affect the individual's behavior in such a way that behaviors matching moral norms create the feelings of pride and honor in the them, while, those not conforming to moral norms create the feelings of sin and regret (Abrahamse et al., 2009). The theoretical framework of this research is a combination of TPB, IBM, NAM and UTAUT, together with other studies about the factors affecting land use change. In fact, being theory-based is one of the features of this research. Based on the discussions raised, the theoretical-research model depicted in figure 1 is provided to predict the factors affecting farmers' behavior toward land use change in rural areas of west Azerbaijan so that suitable behavior is adopted in agricultural land use.

Table 1. Conceptualization of the main structures of the research conceptual framework based on TBA, NAM, UTAUT and IBM theories

Main constructs	Definition	Author(s)
Behavior	Believes behavior to be the visible action and response of an individual in a certain condition or background regarding a specific purpose and in a certain time	Ajzen, 1991
attitude towards the behavior	The positive or negative feeling of an individual about a certain behavior	Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975
Intention to behavior	Behavioral intention states the seriousness of the intention and will of the individual to conduct the aimed behavior	Ajzen, 1991
perceived behavioral control	How easy or difficult is a behavior in one's view	Ajzen, 1991
subjective norm	The individual's understanding of how people he believes to be important think and whether or not he should concern their expectations in his behavior	Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975
Performance expectancy	The extent to which an individual believes using the system can benefit him in improving his professional performance.	Venkatesh et al. 2003

Main constructs	Definition	Author(s)
Facilitating conditions	The extent to which an individual believes that there is a technical and organizational foundation to support the system.	Venkatesh et al. 2003
Moral norm	The inner feeling of an individual to conduct a certain behavior which affects his decision making and can predict his behavior	Onwezen et al, 2013
Environmental constraints	By this structure, the environmental constrains causing a certain behavior are meant.	Glanz et.al, 2008
Environmental factors	In this research, by environmental factors, proximity to village, asphalt-paved roads, and being located at a tourist attraction area are meant.	Mohammadzadeh et al, 2020

Figure 1. Theoretical framework of the research

Study Area

West Azerbaijan province with the area of 37412 square kilometers (Oroumieh lake excluded), is located between 44°2' and 47°32' east longitudes and 35°58' and 39° 47' north latitudes, rests on the north west of Iran. Based on the administrative divisions of the year 2022, this province has 19 counties, 40 districts, 47 cities, 113 rural districts, 2793 habituated villages. The total population of this province was 3,445,600 people in the year 2018, out of which 32.93% live in the rural areas (2018 Statistical Yearbook). Map 1 depicts the geographical location of West Azerbaijan Province in Iran.

Map 1. Geographical location of West Azerbaijan province in Iran

3. Methodologies

The present study is a survey research and with respect to numerical analysis of data, it is a quantitative study. The research method is descriptive-correlative. The statistical society of the research is the farmers of the rural regions of West Azerbaijan Province, who were 224896 exploiters in total. Due to the vastness of the nature of the regions under study, stratified sampling was employed. Following administrative divisions, each county has been divided into a number of rural areas (Map 1). Then, the capital of each rural area has been considered as the village to be studied. To set the volume of the sample, Cochran formula was applied and out of 224896 exploiters (farmers) of the region under study, the sample volume was calculated as 599 exploiters (with the error level of 4%). It was tried that at least five farmers be studied from every village. This increased sample volume to the final number of 749 farmers.

To collect the research data based on the research objectives, a questionnaire was developed which was comprised of various sections and had a qualitative scale of five choices (very little=1; Little= 2; average=3 Much=4; very much=5) and the questions were redesigned. Data collection process which had been started from May 2021 took 6 months and the data was collected from 113 rural areas of the counties of West Azerbaijan province. To evaluate the behavior of farmers in change of agricultural land use, this variable was measured based on Ajzen's Definition (Ajzen, 2001) through three questions. Also, in order to evaluate the structure of behavioral intention, attitude toward behavior, subjective norm and control of perceived behavior, the questionnaire developed by Ajzen (Ajzen, 2001) was applied. To measure the performance expectation structure (probability of performance) and the facilities condition (the facilitating conditions), Venkatesh and

Davis's standard questionnaire (Venkatesh and Davis, 2003) were employed. The operational definitions of the variables applied in this research are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Operational Definitions of Research Structures

Structure		Operational Definition
Behavior towards agricultural land and usage change		<p>1. Have you changed the use of your agricultural lands within the last 10 years? 2. If yes, to what extent (in square meters)? 3. If yes, how much have you encouraged other farmers to do the same?</p> <p>To measure the final behavior of land use change in the farmers of the rural areas of West Azerbaijan, since the range of the questions under study differ, the questions were unscalled. To do so, the phase standardization (unscaling) method was applied, which is stated in formula 1: $R_{ij} = \frac{X_{ij} - X_j^{min}}{X_j^{max} - X_j^{min}}$</p> <p>In this formula, X_{ij} is the value of the i^{th} item, X_j^{min} is the i^{th} minimum and X_j^{max} is the i^{th} maximum.</p> <p>Finally, since in phase unscaling, the scale of the questions falls between zero and one, one can add up the value of the three questions and find the behavior of the farmers of the rural districts under study.</p>
Intention to change the use of agricultural land		<p>1. I intend to encourage other farmers to change the use of their productive lands. 2. I am planning to change the usage of my lands 3. In the near future, I intend to change the usage of my lands to change my occupation as a farmer 3. Since change of agricultural land use increases the price of the land, I will do this in near future. To measure the structure "behavior intention", Likert's five-choice scale was employed.</p>
Attitude towards the behavior of agricultural land use change		<p>1. For agricultural lands, change of land use increases the price of the land 2. Farmers have an inalienable right to their agricultural lands and they can use them as they wish 3. I am ready to volunteer to assist preventing agricultural lands use change 4. I do not care if agricultural lands are turned into other uses 5. There are many agricultural lands all over the country and this is not a problem or issue. To measure the structure "attitude toward change of usage of agricultural lands", Likert's five-choice scale was employed.</p>
The structure of subjective norm regarding the change of agricultural land use		<p>1. My family recommends me to change the usage of my productive agricultural lands 2. Most of those whose opinions I care about agree with the change of land use for productive agricultural lands 3. Agricultural promoters and experts expect that the usage of agricultural lands not be changed at all. 4. Just like other farmers who have changed the usage of their lands and earned high profits, I want to change the usage of my lands, too. 5. I usually do what my friends and family advise me to do. 6. I usually do what matters for the society. To measure the structure "Subjective norm about change of usage of agricultural lands", Likert's five-choice scale was employed.</p>
Perceived behavior control structure in the field of agricultural land use change		<p>Considering my economic condition, change of land use is the best means of subsistence for me 2. I can increase my income through changing the use of agricultural lands 3. I lack the necessary knowledge in agriculture and cannot continue farming 4. Since little bank facilities are allocated by the government to develop farming, it is difficult for me to continue this job To measure the structure "Perceived behavior control about change of usage of agricultural lands", Likert's five-choice scale was employed.</p>
The structure of facility conditions in the field of agriculture		<p>1. The government enjoys the required supportive and encouraging policies to take agricultural products under insurance coverage 2. During crises such as drought, the government solves the farmers' problems as much as necessary 3. Agricultural Jihad and land affairs Organizations are trying to enforce the guidelines related to management of agricultural lands and land use change. To measure the structure "facility conditions in the field of agriculture", Likert's five-choice scale was employed.</p>
Performance expectancy	Waiting outcome	<p>If I change the land use of my agricultural lands, I will have a better chance to increase my income 2. By changing the land use, I need to spend less time to perform my regular job tasks. 3. By employing other usages such as garden villas, resorts, etc, I can earn more. To measure the structure "waiting outcome", Likert's five-choice scale was employed.</p>
	Perceived usefulness	<p>1. Agricultural lands use change can endanger the food security of the society 2. If I change the use of my lands, other farmers may do the same, which may, in the end, lead to food scarcity and food price increase. 3. The destructive consequences of agricultural lands use change on national economy and food security is far beyond our knowledge. To measure the structure "perceived usefulness", Likert's five-choice scale was employed.</p>
Ethical norm in the field of agricultural land use change		<p>1. I feel I am a good person if I work on my agricultural lands 2. I feel committed to preserve my agricultural lands 3. I feel if I do not change the usage of my</p>

	agricultural lands, I have taken a useful and effective action in securing food for the society. To measure the structure "Ethical norm", Likert's five-choice scale was employed.
The structure of environmental constraints in the field of agricultural land	1. Water scarcity has practically prevented me from agricultural activities and considering this condition, I have to change the usage of my agricultural lands 2. Climate changes such as droughts and floods have forced me to change the usage of my agricultural lands 3. The status of the soil texture of agricultural lands is in a way that has led to very low performance in agricultural products making them inadequate to cover my living expenses. 4. The agricultural lands I am working on are not farmable. To measure the structure "Environmental constraints", Likert's five-choice scale was employed.
Environmental factors (such as distance and proximity to the road, village limits) in the field of agriculture	1. How far are your agricultural lands from the village? 2. How far are your agricultural lands from asphalt-paved roads? 3. Are your agricultural lands located at a tourist attraction area? To measure the final index "environmental factors", since the scale of the questions under study differ, the questions were unscaled. To do so, the phase standardization (unscaling) method was applied, which was stated in formula 1. Finally, since in phase unscaling, the scale of the questions falls between zero and one, one can add up the value of the three questions and find the final index "environmental factors".

To determine the validity of the questionnaire, face validity method was applied, which was obtained after seeking the opinion of professors and experts and through several stages of review and revision. Also, in order to find the reliability, internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha) and convergent validity were calculated through AVE. Considering the values reported in Table 3, the indices Cronbach's alpha, AVE and CR enjoy high and suitable values. Therefore, it could be concluded that all the selected indices have been corrected chosen to measure the hidden variables (structures) of the research and their reliability and validity is confirmed. Further, to analyze the factors affecting the behavior of change of use in the agricultural lands of the rural areas of West Azerbaijan province, Pearson's Correlation coefficient and Structural equations were applied. Data analysis was conducted through AMOSEve24 software.

Table 3. Reliability and convergent validity of the research constructs in the measurement model

Structure	Number of Item	Cronbach's Alpha	AVE	CR	
Intention to change the use of agricultural land	4	0.861	0.806	0.943	
Attitude towards behavior	5	0.865	0.704	0.922	
subjective norm	6	0.877	0.416	0.810	
perceived behavioral control	4	0.859	0.607	0.861	
Facilitating conditions	3	0.905	0.596	0.815	
Moral norm	3	0.944	0.521	0.765	
Environmental constraints	4	0.735	0.498	0.797	
Performance	Perceived usefulness	3	0.916	0.533	0.773
expectancy	Waiting Outcome	3	0.872	0.491	0.743

Source: Findings of the research

4. Results

Descriptive Analysis of the Personal Characteristics

The descriptive analysis of the individual characteristics of the respondents demonstrates that 95.30% of the subjects are men. Their average age is 44.35 with the standard deviation of 10.41 years. The main occupation of 93.32% of the respondents is

farming and their average records in the farming job is 26.79. Research on the education of those under study showed that their average educational records was 3.74 with the standard deviation of 1.13 years. The area of irrigated lands of the farmers under study was 4.98 acres. Also, the respondents stated that their average monthly income was USD 450. (Table 4).

Table 4. Description of individual characteristics of farmers in rural areas of West Azarbaijan province

Indicators	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age (year)	23	76	44.35	10.41
Education level (year)	0	16	3.74	1.13
Horticultural History (years)	2	59	26.79	11.03
Household dimension (person)	1	8	3.21	0.87
Water lands	0	22	4.98	2.85
Monthly income of farmers (dollars)	60	1840	450.20	215.63

Source: Research Findings

Situational Analysis Of Farmers' Behavior Towards Land Use Change In Rural Areas Of West Azerbaijan Province

One of the objectives of the present research is to measure the variable " the behavior of change of agricultural land use in the farmers of the rural areas of West Azerbaijan province". To this end, first, the index "the behavior of change of agricultural land use" was checked in the form of three questions and the extent to which this behavior was realized in the view of the farmers under study was researched.

Table 5. The status of farmers' behavior towards changing the use of agricultural lands

Indices of land use change	Variable levels	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. D
Have you changed the use of your agricultural land in the last ten years?	Yes	685	91.46	-	-
	no	64	8.54		
If you have changed the land use, how big (in square meters) was it?	-	-	-	7582.18	7032.67
	very little	21	2.80	2.83 ^a	1.29
If you have changed land use, to what extent have you encouraged other farmers to do so?	Low	189	25.23		
	medium	241	32.18		
	Much	173	23.10		
	very much	61	8.14		
	Total	749	100		
Agricultural land use change behavior	-	-	-	0.553 ^b	0.211

Source: research findings Average range: 1 (very little) to 5 (very much) b: The average range is between zero and 1

As depicted by Table 5 and Fig 2 1, the extent of the behavior of agricultural land use change in the rural areas of West Azerbaijan province having the average of 0.553 and the standard deviation of 0.211 (and with the mean range between 0 and 1) stands at the intermediate and above intermediate levels. Also it should be mentioned that 8.54% (64 individuals) of the people understand have had no change of land use.

Figure 2. Evaluation of the behavioral index of agricultural land use change in the rural areas of West Azerbaijan

As demonstrated by Table 6 maximum frequency (43.26%) is for the third cluster. Considering its mean (0.545, with the average range of 0 to 1) the status of this cluster regarding the behavior of farmers towards change of agricultural land use in the rural areas of West Azerbaijan province has been evaluated to be at the average level. Also their first cluster showed the least frequency (8.54%). Based on the mean obtained (0), this cluster enjoys a proper condition regarding the index of farmers' behavior of change of agricultural land use. In fact, it could be stated that this cluster has not had any agricultural land use change. Generally, 61.95% of the farmers of the rural areas of West Azerbaijan province stand at the average to suitable level regarding agricultural land use change. Also, 38.05% of the farmers have demonstrated inappropriate behavior in this regard. In other words, 38.05% of the subjects have had the most land use change.

Table 6. Leveling of the respondents in terms of agricultural land use change index

Clustering	Frequency	Percent	cumulative percentage	Mean	Std. Deviation
suitable (0-0.2)	64	8.54	8.54	0	0
Fairly good (0.2-0.4)	76	10.15	18.69	0.385	0.015
intermediate or average (0.4-0.6)	324	43.26	61.95	0.545	0.047
Relatively inappropriate (0.6-0.8)	199	26.57	88.52	0.683	0.042
inappropriate (0.8-1)	86	11.48	100	0.837	0.035
Total	749	100	-	0.553	0.211

Source: research finding

Further, to study the distribution of the dispersion of farmers' behavior of land use change in the rural areas of West Azerbaijan province, Arc-GISver10.5 was applied. As depicted by Map 2, the calculations made on the behavior of land use change revealed that the villages Zoolachay subsidiary of Salmas County, Firouraq a subsidiary of Khoy, Marhamatabad, a subsidiary of Miandoab and Chaman, a subsidiary of Takab suffer from inappropriate conditions with respect to land use change. In other words, the respondents of these villages have made the most land use changes. So, it could be stated that their behavior of land use change stands at an inappropriate level. Also, the villages Southern Avajiq, a subsidiary of Chalderan, and Western Gachlarat, a subsidiary of Poldasht, stand at a suitable level regarding agricultural land use change behavior. Therefore, it could be stated that the least land use change has occurred in these areas. As shown by Map 2, out of the total 113 villages under study, 4 villages (3.54%) stand at an inappropriate level, and 39 villages (34.51%), 51 villages (45.13%), 17 villages (15.04%), and 2 villages (1.77%) stand at relatively inappropriate, intermediate, fairly good and suitable levels, respectively.

Map 2. Spatial distribution of farmers' behavior index in terms of agricultural land use change in rural areas of West Azarbaijan province

Analysis of Factors Affecting the Behavior of Agricultural Land Use Change in Rural Areas

Since the correlation matrix is the basis for analysis of scientific models, Table 7 demonstrates the correlation between the independent variables with one another and that between independent and dependant variables. Table 7 states that there are positive and significant relations between the dependent, intermediate and independent variables. It is noteworthy to say that based on the calculated VIF and the correlations available (Table 7), there is no collinear relationship between the independent variables of this research.

Table 7. Correlation matrix between research variables

<u>Variabels</u>	VIF	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Behavior	-	1								
behavioral intention	3.93	0.83**	1							
Attitude towards behavior	3.11	0.72**	0.79**	1						
subjective norm	2.19	0.63**	0.62**	0.62**	1					
perceived behavioral control	2.13	0.69**	0.68**	0.63**	0.57**	1				
Moral norm	1.51	-0.53**	-0.55*	-0.49*	-0.4**	-0.4**	1			
Performance expectancy	1.38	0.48**	0.46**	0.47**	0.44**	0.38**	-0.29**	1		
Facilitating conditions	2.00	-0.65**	-0.61*	-0.60*	-0.61*	-0.5**	0.43**	-0.40**	1	
Environmental factors	2.21	0.77**	0.72**	0.62**	0.53**	0.58**	-0.46*	0.40**	-0.53**	1
Environmental constraints	1.73	**0.54	0.54**	0.56**	0.57**	0.46**	-0.35*	**0.38	**0.53	0.44**

** Significance level 0.01

The structural model of the relationship among hidden variables, demonstrating the standard regression coefficients and fit indices has been demonstrated in Figure 3.

$\chi^2= 1097.959$ $df= 590$ $\chi^2 /df=1.861$ $RMSEA=0.034$ $CFI=0.970$
 $GFI=0.927$ $TLI=0.966$ $PRATIO=0.886$ $NFI=0.938$ $IFI=0.970$ $PCFI=0.859$
 $RMR=0.036$

Figure 3. Standardized Estimates measurement model

The Chi-Square divided by degrees of freedom ($\chi^2/DF=1.861$), the Comparative Fit Index (CFI=0.970), the Normed Fit Index (NFI=0.938), Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI=0.966), the Goodness of Fit Index (GFI=0.927), the Incremental Fit Index (IFI=0.970), and Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA=0.034) all state the appropriate fit of the model. As demonstrated by Figure 2, 83% ($R^2=0.83$) of the behavioral intention toward agricultural land use change behavior is expressed by the variables Attitude towards behavior (Estimate =0.410; $p=0.001$), subjective norm (Estimate =0.096; $p=0.001$), moral norm (Estimate = -0.115; $p=0.001$), Perceived Behavioral Control (Estimate =0.177; $p=0.001$), and environmental constraints (Estimate =0.248; $p=0.001$). Examination of the results suggests the significance of the route between the variables Attitude towards behavior, subjective norm, moral norm, perceived behavioral control and environmental constraints, on one hand, and, the variable Behavioral Intention to change the use of agricultural lands, on the other hand, at 1% level (Table 8). Also, 79% ($R^2=0.79$) of the variable agricultural land use change behavior is expressed by the variables Perceived Behavioral Control (Estimate =0.136; $p=0.001$), behavioral intention toward agricultural land use change (Estimate =0.361; $p=0.001$), Facilitating conditions (Estimate =- 0.213; $p=0.001$), and environmental constraints (Estimate =0.247; $p=0.001$). Examination of the results suggests the significance of the route between the said variables and the variable agricultural land use change behavior at 1% level (Table 8)

Table 8. Results of structural equations

	Hypothesis		Estimate *	S.E.	C.R.	P Label	Result
behavioral intention	→	Behavior	0.361	0.008	9.038	0.0001	Confirmed
Attitude towards behavior	→	behavioral intention	0.410	0.049	9.667	0.0001	Confirmed
subjective norm	→	behavioral intention	0.096	0.062	2.256	0.024	Confirmed
perceived behavioral control	→	behavioral intention	0.177	0.043	4.967	0.001	Confirmed
perceived behavioral control	→	Behavior	0.136	0.008	3.861	0.001	Confirmed
Moral norm	→	behavioral intention	-0.158	0.042	-3.802	0.0001	Confirmed
Performance expectancy	→	behavioral intention	0.019	0.034	0.645	0.519	<u>Rejeact</u>
Facilitating conditions	→	Behavior	-0.213	0.009	-6.088	0.001	Confirmed
Environmental factors	→	behavioral intention	0.248	0.097	9.329	0.001	Confirmed
Environmental factors	→	Behavior	0.274	0.019	9.896	0.001	Confirmed
Environmental constraints	→	Behavior	0.034	0.009	1.085	0.278	<u>Rejeact</u>

*Regression Weights

Table 9 shows the direct and indirect effects of affective variables of the model to determine the extent of the total effect of every variable mentioned on the structure, agricultural land use change behavior. Examination of direct and indirect effects in the model demonstrates that the variable "behavioral intention to change agricultural land use" having the total effect of 0.361 has the highest effect on the behavior of agricultural land use change of the rural areas of West Azerbaijan province. After this variable, the variables "environmental constraints" (total effect=0.307), "facilitating conditions" (total effect= 0.242), "Perceived behavioral control" (Total effect=0.201), "Attitude towards Behavior" (total effect=0.148), "moral norm" (total effect =0.057) and "subjective norm" (total effect=0.035), respectively, stand at the next places in affecting the behavior of agricultural land use change in rural areas of West Azerbaijan province.

Table 9. Direct and indirect effects of factors influencing the behavior of agricultural land use change in rural areas of West Azarbaijan province

Structure	Indirect Effect	Direct Effect	Total Effect
behavioral intention	0	0.361	0.361
Environmental factors	0.090	0.274	0.307
Facilitating conditions	0	-0.213	-0.242
perceived behavioral control	0.065	0.136	0.201
Attitude towards behavior	0.148	0	0.148
Moral norm	-0.057	0	-0.057
subjective norm	0.035	0	0.035

5. Discussions and Conclusion

The results obtained from measurement of the behavior of agricultural land use change in the rural areas of West Azerbaijan province demonstrate that the condition of the farmers in this field stands at an average level. In fact, it could be stated that change of land use is being practiced at an average level in the productive lands of these areas. Also, other results show that 47.05% of the individuals under study have a high level of land use change behavior. Route analysis findings revealed that out of the total 9 variables given to the model (i.e., behavioral intention to change the agricultural land use, performance expectation, social norms toward change of agricultural land use, attitude towards behavior, perceived behavioral control, subjective norm toward change of land use, environmental factors such as proximity to the village, tourist attraction areas or roads, environmental constraints and facilitating conditions, the relation of 7 variables with the behavior of land use change was found to be significant. Among all, the structures of behavioral intention to change the use of agricultural lands with the total effect of 0.361, environmental factors with the total effect of 0.307, facilitating conditions in agriculture with the total effect of 0.242, moral norm toward change of agricultural lands use with the total effect of 0.057, and finally, social norms with the total effect of 0.035 have respectively had the highest effect on the behavior of agricultural land use change in the rural areas of West Azerbaijan province.

Considering the effectiveness of the variable perceived behavioral control on the behavior, the findings are in line with those of the researches conducted by Yousefvand et al. (Yousefvand et al., 2019) and Doran et al. (Doran et al., 2020); regarding the variable facilitating conditions, the results are in line with those obtained by Savari et al. (Savari et al., 2021). Also, concerning the effectiveness of the variable performance probability, the findings are not in line with those obtained by Gil et al. (Gil et al., 2017).

Moreover, since the variables of subjective norm and attitude have a significant relationship with the variable of behavioral intention, it could be stated that those with an appropriate attitude toward change of agricultural land use together with those under social pressure to accept the change of land use behavior are more willing to conduct the behavior of change of agricultural land use, which is in line with the findings of Savari et al. (Savari, et al., 2021; Asrari et al, 2022). This result particularly confirms TRA, Technology Acceptance Model and UTAUT model. Clark-Richardson (Clark-Richardson, 2003), Boon Yuen and Mohammad Azree (Boon Yuen and Mohammad Azree, 2005) and Lu et al. (Lu et al., 2009) also concluded that subjective norms and attitudes are among the factors affecting behavioral intention. Further, the significant effect of Perceived Behavioral Control on

Behavioral Intention is in conformity with TPB. This finding confirms the results obtained by Terry and O'Leary (Terry and O'Leary, 1995), Van den Putte (Van den Putte, 1993), and Boon Yuen and Mohammad Azree (Boon Yuen and Mohammad Azree, 2005), suggesting the direct and positive effectiveness of perceived (tangible) behavioral control. Also, the findings of the studies conducted by Clark-Richardson (Clark-Richardson, 2003), Bock and Kim (Bock and Kim, 2002), Chow and Chan (Chow and Chan, 2008), Ozer and Yilmaz (Ozer and Yilmaz, 2010), and Ryu et al. (Ryu et al., 2003) demonstrated that subjective norms and attitudes are among the predictors of behavioral intention, while, the results of Chang's research (Chang, 1998) suggested that subjective norm, as an indicator, has no significant relationship with behavioral intention. The structure "environmental constraints" is a significant predictor for the internal variable of agricultural land use change behavior. The coefficient of standardized route for each unit of change in the structure "environmental constraints" gives 0.248 unit of change in the variable "agricultural land use change behavior", which confirms the findings of Mohammadzadeh et al. (2020), Qarani Arani et al. (2019), and Amirnezhad (2013). Furthermore, the variable "moral norm" is a significant predictor for the variable "behavioral intention to change agricultural land use"; this finding confirms NAM theories.

Based on the results obtained by this study, one can design and suggest the model of agricultural land use change behavior in the rural areas of West Azerbaijan province (Fig 4).. Just like any other behavioral model, behavioral intention is a direct predictor of the behavior of agricultural land use change in this model, which is, in turn, affected by the structures of attitude, perceived behavioral control, subjective norm, facilitating conditions, environmental factors, environmental constraints and moral norm. Additionally, facilitating conditions, perceived (tangible) behavioral control, environmental factors and environmental constraints directly affect the behavior of agricultural land use change.

Figure 4. Pattern of resilience behavior against climate change with emphasis on food security

In the end, based on the findings of this research, a few suggestions could be made to improve the status of agricultural land use change behavior among the farmers of the rural areas of West Azerbaijan province.

Findings obtained from the analysis of structural equations show that the structure "behavioral intention to change the agricultural land use" directly affects the behavior of change of agricultural land use. Therefore, informing and increasing the awareness of villagers and farmers about the importance of application of modern agricultural methods in

the condition of climate change, holding training and briefing programs and courses about how to use insurance mechanisms for agricultural and garden products, and cultivating products resistant to draught, etc. can help alter the intention of farmers to change the usage of their agricultural lands so that they are discouraged from approaching land use change.

The structure "facilitating conditions" directly affects the structure "agricultural land use change behavior" in the rural areas under study. "Facilitating conditions" is defined as the extent to which the individual believes that there are organizational and technical infrastructures to support and apply the system. In fact, this structure indicates the understanding of consumers about the available sources and supports to conduct a certain behavior. Therefore, to decrease the area of agricultural land whose use has changed in the areas under study, this structure can be improved through the following actions: promoting the mechanism of covering garden and agricultural products under insurance, providing credits and facilities with appropriate payback conditions, founding contingency reserve funds for farmers, whether as self-governed funds or government-aided ones, creating institutional capacities through qualitative and quantitative development of agricultural societies, founding financial funds, village cooperatives or any other NGOs, and, finally, improving the welfare conditions of farmers through creation of job opportunities and revenues from complementary non-agricultural sections.

Perceived behavioral control causes the increase of the area the land whose use has changed both directly and indirectly and through affecting the structure "behavioral intention". The better the condition of internal controls (including skills and capabilities) and external controls (such as access to financial sources, credits, etc.), the more the farmers are encouraged to change the usage of their agricultural lands, which, finally, leads to increased areas with land use change in the rural areas under study. To solve this issue, training and skill development courses aimed at explaining the disadvantages of land use change can help improve this structure in the future.

The structure "attitude", indirectly, and by affecting the structure "behavioral intention" causes the increase of the behavior of agricultural land use change in the rural areas under study. Therefore, the attitudes of farmers toward their agricultural lands can be enhanced through educational programs shown in media and by conducting promotional activities in the Agricultural Jihad Organization. In fact, long-term strategies need to be sought to improve the promotional programs aimed at improvement of farmers' attitudes toward preservation of agricultural lands.

The structure "social norms", indirectly, and through affecting the structure "behavioral intention" causes increased areas with land use change in the rural areas under study. Thus, controlling the stressful and frustrating atmosphere existing among the farmers and hindering the influence of farmers on one another regarding change of land use through drafting appropriate empowerment programs and encouraging them to contribute can reduce the effect of this structure in changing the usage of agricultural lands, which can finally lead to decrease of the areas with changed land use in the rural areas under study.

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